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FORCED DEGRADATION STUDY FOR ESTIMATION OF RELATED SUBSTANCES AND DEGRADANTS IN ALLOPURINOL TABLET AND ITS METHOD VALIDATION USING RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A precise & accurate stability-indicating analytical method was developed & validated for the estimation of related substances and degradants of allopurinol tablets. Stressed Conditions like exposure to acidic media (5N HCl), basic media (5N NaOH), oxidative media (10% H₂O₂), and photolytic degradation (254 nm) at room temperature and thermal degradation of tablets at 80°C were conducted in order to develop a rapid and sensitive stability indicating Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP- HPLC) method. Allopurinol tablets showed significant degradation under all stress conditions and no peak observed at the retention time of allopurinol in the forced degradation study and degradation was under ICH limits. The method was linear in the range of 0.051–0.760 µg/mL (10%-150%) allopurinol concentrations. Accuracy was determined by spiking allopurinol tablet solution with known impurities. Excellent recoveries of Impurities A, B, C (96 – 98.18 %) proved that the method was sufficiently accurate. The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) of allopurinol were found to be 0.02µg/mL and 0.05µg/mL respectively. The LOD and LOQ of Impurity A, Impurity B and Impurity C were also determined. It was concluded that the developed method was precise and accurate for the determination of allopurinol and its degradants.

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INTRODUCTION

Allopurinol (1H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-ol) is a commonly used in the treatment of chronic gout or hyper uricaemia associated in different pathological or diagnostic conditions like leukaemia, radiotherapy, antineoplastic agents, inflammation and treatment with diuretics conditions[1-5]. It is a structural isomer of hypoxanthine (a naturally occurring purine in the body), purine analogue and acts to inhibit xanthine oxidase[6-7]. Allopurinol will be converted to alloxanthine in the presence of xanthine oxidase, after that the formation of uric acid from xanthine and hypoxanthine will be inhibited. In addition to blocking uric acid production, inhibition of xanthine oxidase causes an increase in hypoxanthine and xanthine, which were converted to closely related purine ribotides adenosine and guanosine monophosphates[8-9]. Ribotides increased levels causes feedback inhibition of amidophosphoribosyl transferase, the first and rate-limiting enzyme of purine biosynthesis. Allopurinol, therefore, decreases both uric acid formation and purine synthesis.

Several spectrophotometric methods were reported for analysis of Allopurinol including [10-11], high performance liquid chromatography[12-13], liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry. A study of forced degradation, degradation kinetics and photo stability of allopurinol [14] were also reported in literature. All impurities found in Allopurinol USP are shown in figure 1.

Legend of figures

Figure 1 Chemical structure and name: (a) Allopurinol; (b) & (c) Degradants; (d) Impurity A; (e) Impurity B; (f) Impurity C; (g) Impurity D; (h) Impurity E; (i) Impurity F.

It was observed that Allopurinol tablets contains only Impurity A, B and C. It is requires to perform stress testing for elucidation of inherent stability characteristics of the active substance according to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline entitled 'stability testing of new drug substances and products'. Hydrolytic, oxidative, thermal and photolytic stability should be determined [15]. Therefore it is necessary to develop a method of force degradation study of allopurinol and its impurities.

The basic aim of the study was to develop an accurate method and validate compatible stability indicating HPLC method for determination of allopurinol and its impurities.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and Reagents

Allopurinol USP secondary reference standard, % Assay (as is): 99.82 (USP) Impurity A CRS, Impurity B CRS, and Impurity C CRS, was purchased from Merck. Other chemical Hydrogen peroxide 30 % solution (AR) purchased from S.D. Fine chem, Hydrochloric acid (AR) from Rankem, Sodium hydroxide from Qualigens Fine Chem (India), and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (AR grade) purchased from S.D. Fine chem..

Mobile phase: - for the preparation of mobile phase 1.25 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate dissolved in 1000mL of Milli-Q water.

Preparation of Test & blank solutions

About 20 allopurinol tablets (300mg) were crushed and weighed accurately about 90 mg of Allopurinol tablet powder, transferred the powder into a 100-mL volumetric flask and 5mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide was added on it. Shake the solution mechanically for about 10 minutes and Diluted up to 100ml with mobile phase. Blank solution was prepared by diluting 5.0mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide with 100mL of mobile phase. Both solutions were filtered through 0.45 µm nylon membrane filter.

Chromatographic system

HPLC system (Waters 2695 Alliance Separation Module) equipped with inbuilt auto sampler and quaternary gradient pump with an on-line degasser was used with Column (Thermo Electron Corporation), Hypersil ODS, C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 µm. It consists of Ultraviolet (PDA/UV) Detector (2996/2487). Mobile phase was degassed before use. The flow rate of mobile phase was 1.5mL/minute with isocratic mode. The runtime was set for 22min, Auto sampler temperature was maintained to 8°C and the injection volume was 20µL.

METHOD

Forced Degradation Study

This studies were performed for the determine of degradation pathways and products degradation during storage, and facilitate formulation development, manufacturing, and packaging [16-18].

Acid induced degradation

90mg allopurinol tablet powder was dissolved in 5mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide, then added 20mL of mobile phase and treated with 2.0mL of 5N hydrochloric acid, kept at room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was neutralized with 2mL of 5N sodium hydroxide and diluted with mobile phase.

Alkali induced degradation

90mg allopurinol tablet powder was dissolved in 5mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide, then added 20mL of mobile phase and treated with 2.0mL of 5N sodium hydroxide, kept at room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was neutralized with 2mL of 5N hydrochloric acid and diluted with mobile phase.

Oxidation induced degradation

About 90mg of allopurinol tablet powder was dissolved in 5mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide. 20mL of mobile phase was added and treated with 2.0mL of 10% hydrogen peroxide, kept at room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was diluted with mobile phase and mixed.

Photolytic degradation

About 90mg of Allopurinol tablet powder was dissolved in 5mL of 0.1N sodium hydroxide. 20mL of mobile phase was added and sample solution was exposed under UV light 254 nm for 72 hours.

Thermal Degradation

Thermal degradation was carried out using different media (acid, alkali, oxidation) solution kept at 80°C for 1hr.

- Thermal degradation of Acidic solution,
- Thermal degradation of Alkaline solution,
- Thermal degradation of 10% Hydrogen peroxide solution,
- Thermal degradation of test as such solution kept for 48 hrs

Validation of Method

Validation is required for any new or amended method, to ensure that the method is capable to giving reproducible and reliable results [19], whenever it is followed by either different operators or different laboratories [20-21] .

Precision

The % RSD for Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C (six replicates) and that of Allopurinol (six replicates) in resolution solution (a) were calculated. The %RSD of test solution in six replicates was determined, and all are within the acceptance criteria i.e. below 10% shown in table II.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was determined by changing conditions i.e. different day, different Instrument with different column and Reagents.

Linearity and Range

The linearity study was carried out for Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C and Allopurinol standard solution at LOQ (Limit of Quantitation) to 150 % of the specification limit. The linearity of Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C and Allopurinol standard was evaluated using HPLC system of Shimadzu, Model: SPD 20A with Column: Hypersil ODS, C18, 250 x 4.6mm, 5 µm. Make: kromacil corporation and the results shown in table II.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

The approach based on the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration plot, it was used for determination of limits of detection and quantification. The LOD and LOQ of Allopurinol, Impurity A, Impurity B and Impurity C were found to be within limit and shown in table II.

Accuracy/Recovery

The recovery study was carried out for Impurity A, Impurity B and Impurity C at LOQ level, 50%, 100% and 150% of the specification limit. The recovery solutions were prepared by spiking the Impurity A, Impurity B and Impurity C solution in Allopurinol tablets shown in table II.

ROBUSTNESS

In all the deliberate varied chromatographic conditions (flow rate, column temperature, detector wavelength), results was found to be within acceptance criteria. The absolute difference was not more than 0.05 by the value obtained from repeatability study for known impurity, maximum unknown impurity and total unknown impurity. The resolution between impurity B and allopurinol is greater than 1.1, shown in table II.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Forced Degradation Study

The criteria for the development of a successful HPLC method that should be able to determine related substances and degradants within 20minutes of runtime and should be accurate, reproducible, robust, indicative of stability and free of interference from degradation products. Impurities are enough for routine use in a quality control laboratory. The results of force degradation study were summarized in table I.

Table I Summary of Forced degradation Study of Allopurinol.

Conditions	% Impurity A	% Impurity B	% Impurity C	%Total unknown impurity	Remark
As such (immediately)	0.03	0.01	Not detected	Not detected	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Acidic condition (for 2hr)	0.01	0.01	Not detected	Not detected	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Alkali condition (for 2hr)	0.01	0.02	Not detected	Not detected	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Oxidative condition (10% H ₂ O ₂) (for 2hr)	0.003	0.04	Not detected	2.2	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Acidic condition (5N HCl + 80°C)	0.13	0.06	Not detected	0.18	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Alkali condition (5N NaOH + 80°C)	0.84	0.090	Not detected	0.30	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Oxidative condition (10% H ₂ O ₂ + 80°C)	0.95	1.90	0.068	4.70	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Thermal condition (for 72 hours)	0.03	0.01	Not detected	Not detected	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity
Photolytic condition (UV 254 nm for 72 hours)	0.01	0.02	Not detected	Not detected	Allopurinol Peak Passes In peak purity

Allopurinol tablets showed significant degradation under stress conditions like acid, alkali, oxidative and other thermal degradation. The chromatogram of acidic degradation and thermal degradation of 10% Hydrogen peroxide solution of Allopurinol were shown in figure 2 and 3 respectively.

Figure 2 Represented Chromatogram of Acidic degradation of Allopurinol.

Figure 3 Chromatogram of Thermal degradation of 10% Hydrogen peroxide solution showing maximum degradation.

The purity angle Allopurinol was less than the Purity threshold, which indicates that the peak due to Allopurinol was pure and there was no co-eluting peaks occurring at the retention time of Allopurinol. The unaffected assay of Allopurinol in presence of degradation product confirms the stability indicating power of the method. Percentage RSD is less than 10.0% confirming the good precision of the method, ruggedness within in the acceptance criteria. The correlation coefficient obtained was greater than 0.999 for all impurities and Allopurinol USP, indicating a linear response of the impurities and drug. Concentration range for Impurity A, B, C and Allopurinol was found to be $0.051- 1.530\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, $0.020- 1.530\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, $0.010- 1.470\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $0.051- 0.76\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively. The LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of Impurities A, B, C and Allopurinol USP were 0.02, 0.01, 0.01 and 0.02 respectively. The LOQ of Impurities A, B, C, and Allopurinol USP were 0.05, 0.02, 0.025 and 0.05 respectively. The impurities were found to be within the acceptance limit after performing robustness studies by changing flow rate, detector temperature and detector range, results are shown in table II.

Table II Validation data.

Conditions	Impurity A	Impurity B	Impurity C	Allopurinol
Precision(%RSD)				
Ref. solution	1.41	0.92	0.75	2.01
Test solution	5.12	1.55	NA	0.47
Ruggedness	6.83	8.29	-	
Linearity				
r	0.9999	0.9998	0.99723	0.99959
Slope	22709.76	32708.09	9413.6	22901.5
Y intercept	248.63	36.78	401.17	89.90
Range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.051- 1.530	0.020- 1.530	0.010- 1.470	0.051- 0.76
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.05	0.02	0.025	0.05
Accuracy/ recovery	98.18	96.0	98.13	
Robustness (resolution)				
Flow rate change				
1.3 mL/min	4.102	8.097	-	10.078
1.7 mL/min	3.516	7.426	-	10.070
Temperature change				
6°C	3.712	7.624	-	10.104
10 °C	3.512	7.980	-	10.154
Detector range				
228nm	3.530	7.408	-	10.074
232nm	3.869	7.786	-	10.212

CONCLUSION

A simple, RP-HPLC method was developed for the quantification of allopurinol and its related substances and degradants. This method was found to be specific, precise, accurate, linear and rugged for the detection as well as quantification of related substances and degradants of allopurinol and also validated. Impurities level increases in alkali and oxidation media. The drug solution was also stable at 8°C within 4hrs. Therefore, it should be used within 4hrs. This study recommends the use of this method in more formulation of allopurinol for accurate determination of components and its degradants.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None

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